

Augurs' Wand Present *Phosphene*

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1 Program Notes

Augurs' Wand is a live audio-visual performance duo using a custom audio-laser synthesiser, *Phosphene*. With this system, the same electrical voltages that produce sound simultaneously drive analogue laser projection. Inspired by early visual music pioneers like the Whitney Brothers and Jordan Belson, their work targets sensory dedifferentiation and synaesthesia. Rather than treating image and sound as separate, mapped media, the performance approaches the electrical signal as a pre-sensory material whose behaviour is perceived across modalities.

Geometric figures function as organising principles embedded within this signal architecture, shaping the evolution of motion, timbre, and colour. These forms—ranging from mathematical fractals to neolithic symbols—act as perceptual anchors that orient the audience towards personal narratives. By interrogating their material tendencies, Augurs' Wand situates signals within a plasma cosmology where geophysical processes, like lightning, suggest origin points of early human myths.

Fig. 1. A still of Augurs' Wand's Performance.

2 Project Description

Augurs' Wand performs using *Phosphene*, a custom audio-laser synthesis environment developed by the duo within the VCV Rack virtual modular ecosystem. This framework supports high-density patching where sonic and visual behaviors emerge from the same signal logic.

The performance employs three independent laser projectors treated as a single compositional instrument. Stereo signals drive each laser's X and Y trajectory, while colour channels are shaped by harmonic relationships, modulation, and inter-laser phase coupling. Signal relationships are shaped in real time, allowing sonic and visual organisation to emerge through interaction rather than pre-composition.

Fig. 2. Performance Signal Flow

3 Technical Notes

This is a live laser and sound performance.

The work is semi-improvised within a fixed system architecture.

Duration: approximately 15-22 minutes

The performers are positioned on stage with a clear line of sight to the projection field while facing forward.

4 Media Link(s)

- Video: <https://vimeo.com/1164537704?fl=ip&fe=ec>

Acknowledgments

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Ethical Standards

This work contains intense laser imagery, high-contrast visual patterns, and loud sound levels. Appropriate warnings will be posted and announced prior to the performance. All laser usage will comply with local safety regulations and venue requirements.

References

- [1] D. Holzer, *Vector Synthesis: A Media Archaeological Investigation into Sound-Modulated Light*. Aalto University, 2019.
- [2] A. Novello, *Media Archaeology-Based Visual Music*. *Musica/Tecnologia*, vol. 15, pp. 7–30, 2021.